

Some New Fuzzy Square Divisor Cordial Graphs

S. Merina

Reg.No: 241111712017, Full Time Ph.D. Research Scholar
Department of Mathematics, Rani Anna Government College for Women
Gandhi Nagar, Palayapettai, Tirunelveli
(Affiliated to Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli.)

Dr. S. Yahya Mohamed

Associate Professor, Department of Mathematics
Rani Anna Government College for Women, Gandhi Nagar, Palayapettai, Tirunelveli
(Affiliated to Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli)

மலர்: 13

சிறப்புத்திட்டம்: 2

மாதம்: சூன் 2025

வருடம்: 2025

P-ISSN: 2321-788X

E-ISSN: 2582-0397

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.16899937](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16899937)

Abstract

In this paper we introduce a new concept called fuzzy divisor cordial labelling. It is a conversion of crisp graph into fuzzy graph under the new condition namely fuzzy divisor cordial labelling. In divisor cordial labelling it is not possible to label all the crisp graphs due to the condition of its definition. Suppose if we consider a graph of size 5, it will be possible to label all the vertices as in the combination of vertex set $\{1,2,3,4,5\}$. So, for n vertices, we need to label all the vertices as a combination of all the vertices without repetition, without neglecting any vertex among them. Here discussion about the edge labelling is trivial. So, it is clear that all the crisp graphs can't be divisor cordial graphs. However in fuzzy divisor cordial graph for any vertices we can label any fuzzy membership value from $[0,1]$. Since the interval consists of infinite number of terms, there are infinite number of chances for labelling a vertex in fuzzy divisor cordial labelling.

Keywords: Fuzzy, Divisor, Cordial, Vertex, Labelling, Trivial

Introduction

The definition of fuzzy graph was first introduced by Kaufmann in the year 1973, based on L.A. Zadeh's fuzzy relations, introduced in the year 1971. Then a mathematician Azriel Rosenfeld developed the theory of fuzzy graph who considered fuzzy relations on fuzzy sets and in 1975. R.T. Yeh and S.Y. Bang have also introduced various connectedness concepts in fuzzy graph in the same year. Yeh and Bang's approach for the study of fuzzy graphs were motivated by its applicability to pattern classification and clustering analysis. They worked more with the fuzzy matrix of a fuzzy graph, introduced concepts like vertex connectivity $\Omega(G)$, edge connectivity $\Lambda(G)$ and established the fuzzy analogue of Whitney's theorem. They also proved that for any three real numbers a, b, c such that $0 < a \leq b \leq c$, there exists a fuzzy graph G with $\Omega(G) = a$, $\Lambda(G) = b$ and $\delta(G) = c$. Fuzzy graphs have been witnessing a tremendous growth and finding applications in many branches of engineering and technology so far. Rosenfeld has obtained several concepts like bridges, paths, cycles, and trees and established some of their properties. Fuzzy end nodes and cut nodes were studied by K.R.Bhutani. Bhattacharya has established some connectivity concepts regarding fuzzy cut nodes and fuzzy bridges titled "Some remarks on fuzzy graphs".

Def: 1.1

Let $G = (V,E)$ be a graph. A mapping $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ is called binary vertex labelling of G and $f(v)$ is called the label of the vertex v of G under f . For an edge $e = uv$, the induced edge labeling $f^* : E(G) \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ is given by $f^*(e) = |f(u)-f(v)| \leq 1$. Let $vf(0)$ and $vf(1)$ be the number of vertices of graph G having labels 0 and 1 respectively under f and let $ef(0)$ and $ef(1)$ be the number of edges having labels 0 and 1 respectively under f^* .

Def: 1.2

A binary vertex labelling of a graph G is called a cordial labelling if $|vf(0)-vf(1)| \leq 1$ and $|ef(0)-ef(1)| \leq 1$. A graph G is cordial if it admits cordial labelling.

Def: 1.3

Let $G = (V,E)$ be a simple graph and $f : V \rightarrow \{1,2,...|V|\}$ be a bijection. For each edge uv , assign the label 1 if either $f(u)$ divides $f(v)$ or $f(v)$ divides $f(u)$ otherwise label 0. Then f is called a divisor cordial labelling of a graph G if $|ef(0)-ef(1)| \leq 1$.

Def: 1.4

A fuzzy graph $G = (\sigma,\mu)$ is a pair of functions $\sigma : V \rightarrow [0,1]$ and $\mu : V \times V \rightarrow [0,1]$, where for all $u,v \in V$, we have $\mu(u,v) \leq \sigma(u) \wedge \sigma(v)$.

Def: 1.5

A labelling of a graph is an assignment of values to the vertices and edges of a graph.

Def: 1.6

Let $G = (\sigma,\mu)$ be a simple graph and $\sigma : V \rightarrow [0,1]$ be a simple bijection. For each edge uv , assign the label d if either $\lfloor \sigma(u) \rfloor \lfloor \sigma(v) \rfloor$ or $\lfloor \sigma(v) \rfloor \lfloor \sigma(u) \rfloor$ and the label 0 otherwise. σ is called a fuzzy square divisor cordial labelling if $|\epsilon\mu(0)-\epsilon\mu(d)| \leq 1$, where d is a very small positive quantity, which is closure to 0 and $d \in (0,1)$. In other words, a graph with a fuzzy square divisor cordial labelling is called a fuzzy square divisor cordial labelling graph.

Theorem: 1.1

Every Path P_n is a Fuzzy Square Divisor Cordial Graph

Proof:

Case (i)

If n is odd

Then there exists odd vertices and even number of edges

Let $v_0, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n$ be the vertices of path p_n .

$$ef(1) = ef(0) = (n-1)/2$$

Case (ii)

If n is even

Then there exists even vertices and odd number of edges

Label the vertices $v_0, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n$ be the vertices of path p_n with the same order except by interchanging the label of vertices v_2 and v_3 .

Thus, $ef(1) = n/2$ and $ef(0) = (n-2)/2$

$$\text{Hence } |ef(0) - ef(1)| \leq 1.$$

Thus, P_n is divisor cordial.

Theorem: 1.2

Every Wheel graph w_n is a Fuzzy Square Divisor Cordial Graph

Proof:

Case (i)

In a graph

n number of vertices they will $2(n-1)$ edges.

The wheel w_n graph contains $2(n-1)$ edges.

Let $v_0, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n$ be the vertices of wheel graph w_n .

Fix v_0 at the centre point label the remaining vertex by any fuzzy membership function which can't be divided by one another except the centre vertex.

$$\text{Hence } |ef(0) - ef(1)| \leq 1.$$

Illustration

Consider a wheel graph W_9 .

Here $\epsilon\mu(0) = 8$, $\epsilon\mu(d) = 8$

$$|\epsilon\mu(0) - \epsilon\mu(d)| = |8 - 8| = |0| \leq 1$$

Hence $|\epsilon_{\mu}(0) - \epsilon_{\mu}(d)| \leq 1$.

Therefore every wheel graph

W_n is a fuzzy square divisor cordial graph.

Theorem: 1.20

Every cycle C_n is a fuzzy square divisor cordial graph.

Proof

We know that cycle C_n has n number of vertices and n number of edges.

Let $v_0, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n$ be the vertices of cycle C_n .

If n is odd, there exist odd number of edges.

Also if n is even, there exist even number of edges.

Example: 3

Consider cycle graphs C_6 and C_7 .

Cycle C6

Here $\epsilon_{\mu}(0) = 3, \epsilon_{\mu}(d) = 3$

$$|\epsilon_{\mu}(0) - \epsilon_{\mu}(d)| = |3 - 3| = |0| \leq 1$$

Hence $|\epsilon_{\mu}(0) - \epsilon_{\mu}(d)| \leq 1$.

Cycle C7

Here $\epsilon_{\mu}(0) = 4, \epsilon_{\mu}(d) = 3$

$$|\epsilon_{\mu}(0) - \epsilon_{\mu}(d)| = |4 - 3| = |1| \leq 1$$

Hence $|\epsilon_{\mu}(0) - \epsilon_{\mu}(d)| \leq 1$.

Therefore every cycle C_n is a fuzzy square divisor cordial graph

Conclusions

In this paper, we have discussed some mathematical inner beauty of fuzzy square graphs. If we go in to the deep of cordial labeling of crisp graph, we can realize that for every crisp graph, we

can't apply cordial labeling. However it is possible in fuzzy square graphs. Especially in the view of fuzzy divisor cordial graph which plays main role in this paper. Because $|V|$ is finite also every vertex must be labeled in crisp graph. However in fuzzy square graph, there are infinite number of chances to label the vertex from 0 to 1.

So clearly we can conclude that every fuzzy graphs and crisp graphs can be represented in the form of fuzzy square divisor cordial graph. This paper is the strong gateway to prove the above statement.

References

1. Nagoorgani. A and Rajalaxmi(a) subhashini.D, Properties of fuzzy labeling graph, Applied Mathematical Sciences, 6 (70) (2012) 3461–3466
2. Nagoor Gani. A and Rajalaxmi (a) Subhashini. D, A note on Fuzzy labeling", International journal of Fuzzy Mathematical Archive, 2014.
3. Nagoor Gani. A and Rajalaxmi Subhashini. D, Fuzzy Labeling tree" Internal Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics, Volume No. 2 2014, 131-141.
4. Nagoor Gani. A, Muhammad Akram and Rajalaxmi (a) Subhashini. D, „Novel Properties of Fuzzy labeling Graphs" , Research Article, Hindawi, 2014.
5. Rosenfeld. A, Fuzzy Graph, In: Zadeh. L.A, Fu. K.S and Shimura. M, Editors, Fuzzy Sets and their Applications to Cognitive and Decision Process, Academic Press, New York (1975) 77-95.
6. Varatharajan. R, Navaneethakrishnan. S and Nagarajan. K, Divisor cordial graphs, International J.Math. Combin. Vol.4(2011), 15-25.
7. Varatharajan. R, Navaneethakrishnan. S and Nagarajan. K, Special classes of divisor cordial graphs, International Mathematical Forum, Vol.7, 2012, no. 35, 1737-1749.
8. Yahya Mohamad. S, Suganthi. S, Properties of Fuzzy Matching in Set Theory, Journal of Emerging technologies and Innovative Research, Vol.5, issue 2, July 2018.
9. Yahya Mohamad. S, Suganthi. S, Energy of Complete Fuzzy Labeling Graph through Fuzzy

- Complete Matching, International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology, Vol.58, issue 3, June 2018.
10. Yahya Mohamad. S, Suganthi. S, Matching and Complete Matching Domination in Fuzzy Labelling Graph, Journal of Applied Science and Computations, Journal of Applied Science and Computations, Vol.5, issue 10, Oct 2018.
11. Yahya Mohamad. S, Suganthi. S, Some Parameters of fuzzy labeling tree using matching and Perfect matching, Malaya Journal of Matematik, Vol.S, NO.1, 511-514, 2020.